

DESIGN OF PRINTED PRODUCTS

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Annotation: This article describes in detail the design of printed products, the implementation of the printing process, the variety of printing products in the modern world, the specialization of printing workers and the division of labor with the development of typography.

Key words: printed products, design, typography, division of labor, printing.

Introduction:

A professional and responsible approach is very important both in the implementation of the printing process and in preparation for this process. Most of the best option is the production of printed products - custom design, pre-press and printing in one enterprise, in this case, the manufacturer's specialists can and should be responsible for the result, as well as the quality, at all stages of product preparation.

In the modern world, printing production is distinguished by the variety of products and the technologies used in their production. Such stratification of demand leads to significant fluctuations in production and technical parameters of publications - formats, sizes, circulation. In such conditions, quick, professional and correct response to changes is required. For this, it is necessary to know the technologies, techniques and specific features of printing.

Literature analysis and methodology:

They usually bring a ready-made layout of the product, which must be adapted by the printing specialists to the specifics of the specific production. However, in any case, we satisfy the client's wishes: we prepare for the release of products that meet their most diverse requirements, we optimize existing schemes for creating a printed product.

The printing of information presented in the form of text, numerical data, tables, mathematical and other formulas is called visual information. Traditionally, a printing company had two separate departments, one that processed textual data and the other that processed images. Combining text and image data is done in the third section, where the location of a particular publication is done.

A printing element is a part of a form that receives printing ink and then transfers it to the printing material. The void elements are areas that do not receive ink by themselves, and therefore these areas on the printed material are not covered by the ink layer. The formation of printed elements in the form can be done due to their spatial separation or the creation of different physico-chemical or other properties of printed and free elements. The printing process is done in a printing press which requires ink and printing material.

Social-pedagogical problems of developing technical creativity of technical creativity and design students, organizational bases of technical creativity activities, invention, discovery, rationalization proposals and patent information, methods of solving technical creativity issues, design and modeling, design basics, technical modeling and construction, students' technical creativity It is planned to provide knowledge on topics related to guiding creativity

activities, organizing technical creativity activities in classroom and extracurricular institutions, methods of developing students' technical creativity.

Graphic design has very deep historical roots. In fact, it appeared at the same time as the development of industrial printing and printing technologies. However, the principles and techniques of print design are shared by traditional painting, sculpture and other classical art forms with centuries of history.

Digital halftone processors such as laser printers can only produce dots of a precise size. To simulate dots of variable size, these devices group spots of fixed size into a matrix called a halftone cell. The number of potential tones that a given halftone cell can reproduce depends on both the line of the screen and the dimensions of the printing device, but a single halftone cell can reproduce only one shade of gray.

Results:

At the same time, the design of printed products largely depends on printing technologies. For example, the same layout printed on a color laser printer and an offset machine will look different. Despite the continuous improvement of printing systems and the use of digital technologies, today there is no universal way to create a layout that can be equally well reproduced using different printing methods.

If the designer has a bad idea about the technology on which his model will be printed, the possibility of mistakes is very high. On the other hand, a designer who knows well which equipment and how the print will be printed can maximize the benefits of the chosen printing method and ensure a high quality of the finished product. A well-made layout is error-free, high-quality and displayed in the shortest possible time.

It is known that the creation of handwritten books in ancient times required the work of many scribes. In the Middle Ages, the printing method began to be used, in which wooden boards were used. Such a board is covered with paint using special pads, after which paper is applied to it and wrapped with leather rolls.

However, this method was not perfect enough to create any voluminous compositions, as each page required a hand-made wooden board. The next step in the development of printing was the invention of individual letters, obtained by casting from a solvent material, with which words could be typed.

All raster editors allow you to easily change the size and resolution of a raster image, but before performing such operations, it is necessary to take into account some features specific to raster images. The quality of a bitmap image directly depends on the number of pixels it contains.

At the same time, the amount of space occupied by the image on the hard disk and the time it takes to process or print it directly depends on the number of pixels, as well as the color model used. If you reduce the size of the image while the number of pixels remains the same, its dimensions will increase, that is, the quality will improve. By increasing the size of the image, on the contrary, the number of pixels decreases and the quality of the image deteriorates - if the number of pixels is too low, it starts to look like a mosaic.

An 18th-century printing house was an impressive enterprise in terms of size and number of employees, consisting of several departments: an office where orders were received and payments were made; typing rooms or entire halls, where compositors and meter-pagers perform layout and typesetting, as well as typesetting corrections on manual machines;

department of printing machines, where printed works are printed on machines; an engine room containing a steam engine or other engine that drives printing machines; a warehouse where stocks of paper, fonts, paints and other materials are stored.

Knowledge of printing technology, at least in a general sense, allows the designer to better prepare the layout and avoid marriage. When preparing layouts for printing, it is necessary to take into account some limitations related to the characteristics of image reproduction in various media and the physical nature of color perception.

Discussion:

In addition, a wide range of different techniques and programs for computer processing of text and graphics requires in-depth knowledge in this field. Considering that many technologies have been developed in the last 10-15 years, it is not surprising that there are still not many experienced digital printing professionals. As for the preparation of documents for publication on the Internet, this field is still young, which also creates certain difficulties.

Almost all literature around us is printed in printing houses. A few decades ago, this was practically the only way to achieve mass circulation. Only in recent years has equipment appeared that allows for low-cost production of small and medium-sized series of full-color printed products, no less than quality printed products. These are primarily color laser printers and digital copiers, as well as risographs and copiers.

The methods of semitone transmission in analog and digital processes are fundamentally different. The point is that the image of a black-and-white photograph is built on the basis of randomly located points, each of which can have its own shade of gray. When using digital printing methods, it is physically impossible to use a separate ink to convey each shade. Therefore, only one black ink is used to print black and white images.

In this case, halftones are transmitted using a raster - a set of completely black dots arranged in a certain order. Thus, typographic reproduction of grayscale images is based on an optical illusion - the human eye sees gray color, although only black color is used to create the image.

It is known that the quality of the print largely depends on the paper on which it is printed. The same printed product can look completely different on different types of paper, so the designer must have a good idea of the result of printing on a particular paper. Before developing the original layout, it is necessary to determine what paper will be used to print it, and this should be taken into account during development. There are a number of specific requirements for the paper used in printing. The properties of offset paper are determined by the use of moisture in the printing process, the high viscosity of the inks used, and the sensitivity of printed forms to mechanical and chemical influences.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it should be said that many enterprises and organizations have established their own publishing groups and departments for the preparation of advertising and printed products within the enterprise. This will definitely have a positive effect, because the customer can quickly get the necessary products without contacting specialized companies. However, at the same time, many people who did not have special education and were not familiar with traditional typography came to printing, which inevitably led to a lot of problems and a high percentage of defects.

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